

Nano-molar Ag ion detection using ZnS QDs in the UV-Vis technique without organic mediator

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Abstract

Ag shows large applications e.g. excellent electrical and thermal conductors, metal reflectors, anti-bacterial uses and in jewel industries. However, it is found to be hazardous and potent threat to health and environment [1]. The environmental protection agency has set maximum contaminant level for Ag at 0.1 mg/L (0.93 μ M) and therefore it warrants to be detected at low concentration.

We report, for the first time, an ultra small amount of Ag⁺ detection without using any organic component as mediator by a simple UV-Visible (UV-Vis) technique. Quantum dots of ZnS prepared in a soft chemical route are utilized for detection [2]. UV-Vis and photoluminescence measurements decipher quantum confinement effect and various defects in ZnS nanoparticles, respectively. Defect band in ZnS nanoparticles prominently appears at 400 – 550 nm in UV-Vis region and is used for Ag⁺ detection in aqueous solution. This defect containing surfaces in ZnS allow the formation of insoluble precipitate of Ag₂S, which is confirmed using X-ray diffraction measurement. In consequence, total absorption of ZnS NPs is affected providing platform for quantitative estimation for Ag⁺ detection for a wide range of concentrations starting from nM to mM. The process is also extended to toxic and heavy elements *e.g.* Pb, Hg and Cd and crucial role of solubility and selective nature of Ag-S interaction are highlighted.

Keywords: ZnS, quantun dots, UV-Vis spectroscopy, Ag, heavy metals

References

1. NR Panyala et al. *Journal of Applied Biomedicine* 6 (2008) 117.
2. R N Juine, et al., *Materials Letters* 128 (2014) 160-162.